

EFFECT OF PERCEIVED RISKS ON THE ADOPTION OF CASHLESS TRANSACTIONS IN JALINGO METROPOLIS AS PERCEIVED BY BANK WORKERS

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Abstract

Cashless policy was recently introduced into Nigerian payment system not more than ten years ago. The introduction of Cashless transactions received a lot of reactions from users and many banks received a lot complaint through their customer care units regarding the fear of perceived risks involved in engaging in it. This paper looked in to effects perceived risks on the adoption of cashless transactions in Jalingo metropolis as perceived by bank workers. Three research questions were formulated from the objectives of the study. Structured questionnaire was used in data collection and Z Test was used in data analysis. It was discovered from the findings of the research work that financial, performance as well as security risks have negative effect on users' behaviours towards the adoption of cashless transactions.

Key Words: Cashless transactions, Financial Risk, Performance Risk, Security Risk

Introduction

Risk according to British English online Dictionary (2020), is the likelihood of a negative outcome or the potential negative effect of an event determined by combining the likelihood of the event occurring with the effect should it occur. Financial risk refers to the potential for monetary loss due to online transactions. Good as the cashless economy may be made to look; the system will come at some costs. The use of POS terminals in the cashless system will attract special charges that do not go with cash transactions. A price tag of 1.25% of the cost of every transaction done through POS terminals will be charged by the operators of the terminals (Akhalumeh and Ohiokha, 2012). This can generate dissatisfaction and consequent resistance to adoption and continuing operation of the cashless economy. The performance risk refers to losses incurred by deficiency or malfunction of online banking websites. Sudden breakdown of web servers may lead to unexpected losses while conducting online transactions. Malfunctions of online banking websites would reduce customers' willingness to accept the cashless policy (Lee, 2009). Security is being defined as a threat which creates "circumstance, condition, or event with the potential to cause economic hardship to data or network resources in the form of destruction, disclosure, modification of data, denial of service and/or fraud, waste, and abuse" (Kalakota and Whinstone, 2007). Under this definition, in the context of cashless transaction threats can be made either through network and data transaction attacks or through unauthorized access to the account by means of false or defective authentication. The issue of security has been mentioned in passing. The issue is a serious one, Nigeria having been described as the hub of internet scam;

one can only wonder how the vulnerability of the cashless system to various forms of internet-related crimes will be addressed.

Statement of the problem

As good as cashless transaction may be, there are limitations it may place on individuals and effects to the populace due to lack of capabilities and facilities to operate it. For instance, in case where there is a global emergency cashless policy may not be adopted by most citizens because most of what individual may need require cash. Another challenge that prompts this article is the fact that we live in a country with internet instabilities which may cause a delay in the use of cashless transactions and the tendency for money loss is inevitable and the security of fund for immediate use is not guarantee. This article will provide an alternative to the use of cashless policy on the citizenry of Taraba State by considering financial risk, security risk and performance risk on the individual and the populace at large.

Purpose of the Study

This paper will probe into the effects of the use of cashless policy among the citizens of Taraba State and her inhabitants as perceived by bank workers as highlighted below:

- i. To determine the effect of financial risk on user's behaviour in adopting cashless transaction in Taraba State.
- ii. To find out the effect of performance risk on user's behaviour in adopting cashless transaction in Taraba State.
- iii. To examine the effect of security risk on user's behaviour in adopting cashless transaction in Taraba State.

Research Questions

- i. What is the effect of Financial Risk on user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions?
- ii. What is the effect of Performance Risk on user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions?
- iii. What is the effect of Security Risk on user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions?

2.0 Review of Related Literatures

2.1.Potential Challenges Associated with Cashless Economy

Though the cashless economy is of enormous importance to national growth, it is not without its own challenges (Wahlert, 2010). For the cashless economy to work, certain factors must be present, not just present but in the right quantity and quality. It is for this reason that many analysts question the readiness of Nigeria for a cashless system, amongst others (Akhahlumeh and Ohiokha, 2012).

The policy faces the danger of payment fraud. Experience of the pilot scheme in Lagos so far, has witnessed high incidence of fraud.

High Rate of illiteracy is another factor. This is a situation where not all targeted populace were literate, while some of them do not know how to make use of the e-banking technologies. For instance, a dubious businessman may decide to deduct more than what the person consumes from an illiterate customer that does not know how to operate the Point of sale (POS) terminal. Illiteracy will, among others, be the greatest impediment in the country's shift towards a cashless society (Nwankwo and Eze, 2012).

Another challenge to the successful implementation of the cashless policy is the inefficiency brought about by poor infrastructure. For example, on many occasions people go to Automated Teller Machine (ATM) to make withdrawals, the cash is not dispensed to them even after the system had debited their accounts. Or there may be problem associated with network failure. Thus, with this, the ATM and POS machines cannot work when the consumers need them.

Public Power Supply is another known infrastructural challenge. Consistent and continuous supply of electricity is essential for effective and efficient e-payment services. Unfortunately, in Nigeria, the power system is very epileptic where it is available and in most rural areas it is non-existent.

Presently, Nigeria occupies an unenviable position among countries in Africa with the largest number of people with no access to financial services. Although the Central Bank of Nigeria in its recent exposure draft on financial inclusion strategy, put the number of adults in the country excluded from financial services as at 2010 at 46.3 percent, most reports on the country believe that the figure is higher than that, as they put it at about 70 percent. Data compiled by Microfinance Information Exchange (MIX) as at the year 2010, showed that Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of Congo were found to have the largest gaps between populations living

in poverty and those with access to financial services, 80 million in Nigeria and 48 million in the Congo (Nweke, 2012).

Instability of Point of Sale (POS) networks, which is prevalent across all operators, would pose a problem and serve as a barrier to usage especially when money sent is not received when needed.

Concerns were also raised about trust in the Agents providing cash-in and cash-out services, this could be risky for customers and the agents if there is no form of security and proper monitoring of operations.

Fear of the unknown - the current banking crisis (both deposit money banks and microfinance banks) has not helped in alleviating the public's fear (Nwankwo and Eze, 2012).

Interoperability of various systems, solutions and applications remain daunting as the technological solutions pose commercial puzzles in ensuring all parties are appropriately rewarded while users obtain efficient services at reasonable prices (Nwankwo and Eze, 2012).

2.2 Benefits and Pitfalls of Cashless System

The world has come from far and we are every day digging into the unknown, what was unthinkable then is now a practice. Today, you can bank right from the comfort of your home and multitudes of benefits come with it. Among other advantages, the major advantages of E-banking are:

- i. Lower operating cost per unit services for banks
- ii. Convenience to customers
- iii. Very low incidence of errors
- iv. Customer can obtain funds at any time from ATM machines and can easily transfer the funds from one place to another place electronically, among other advantages. (CBN, 2012)

3.0 Methodology

Design of Study

The research design adopted was the descriptive survey research design. A descriptive survey design involves the assessment at public opinion using a collection of detailed description of existing phenomena with the aim of using the data to justify current condition and practices or to make better plans for improvement,

Population of the study

The population of the study consists of all bank workers in Jalingo metropolis, making the total of twelve banks.

Sample/sampling techniques

Simple random sampling was used to select ten workers from each bank, making the total of 120 workers to represent the population for this study

Instrument for data collection

A structured questionnaire with a 5-point likert scale was used to collect data. The 5-point Likert ranges from 5=Strongly Agreed, 4=Agreed, 3=Neutral, 2=Disagreed and 1=Strongly Disagreed.

Validation of Instrument

The instrument for data collection was given to expert for face and content validation and was found to be adequate for the purpose of data collection for this research work.

Method of Data Collection

The instrument for data collection was administered personally by the researcher. A total number of 120 questionnaires were distributed and Z test was used as tool for data analysis.

Results and Discussion

The degree of significant was measured using $\alpha = 0.025$ since we are considering a two tail normal distribution which statistical value is given by the standard normal table as 2.56.

. Hypotheses were created and Mean score for each variable is calculated to form the significant value for the responses from data collected

Research Question 1: What is the effect of Financial Risk on user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions?

Hypothesis:

H₀: Financial Risk negatively affect user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions

H₁: Financial risk does not negatively affect user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions

Constructs		SA	A	N	D	SD	REM
1	Fear of losing money due to careless mistakes such as wrong input of account number and wrong input of the amount of money.	3.6	0.8	-1.6	-1.4	-1.5	SA is significant
2	Fear of not getting compensation from banks when errors occur while engaging in cashless transaction.	3.8	1.7	-1.8	-1.8	-1.9	SA significant

From the table above, it was observed that financial risk negatively affects the behaviours of users towards adoption and continued usage of cashless transaction with mean score of 3.6 for fear of losing money due to careless mistakes and wrong input of amount of money and 3.8 for fear of not getting compensation from banks in case of error during online transactions.

Research Question 2: What is the effect of Performance Risk on user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions?

Hypothesis:

H₀: Performance Risk negatively affect user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions

H₁: Performance risk does not negatively affect user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions

Constructs		SA	A	N	D	SD	REM
3	Cashless transaction may not go well because of slow download speeds or servers breakdown.	3.9	-0.3	-1.1	-1.3	-1.2	SA significant
4	Servers may not perform well when conducting Cashless transaction and process payments incorrectly.	3.5	1.1	-1.4	-1.5	-1.6	SA significant

From the table above, Mean score of 3.9 showed that users feel that cashless transaction may not go well for them due to slow download speed or servers' breakdown. Users also feared that servers may not perform well when conducting cashless transactions and process payments incorrectly with Mean score of 3.5.

Research Question 3: What is the effect of Security Risk on user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions?

Hypothesis:

H₀: Security Risk negatively affect user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions

H₁: Security risk does not negatively affect user's behaviour in adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions

Constructs		SA	A	N	D	SD	REM
5	Providing personal privacy information over the Internet is not totally safe.	3.2	1.9	-1.6	-1.6	-1.9	SA significant
6	Other people may be able to access some people's account when using Cashless transactions.	3.6	0.8	-1.4	-1.4	-1.6	SA significant
7	Sending sensitive information online does not give a secure feeling.	3.4	0.9	-1.7	-0.8	-1.8	SA significant

The result from the above showed a Mean score of 3.2 for users fear of providing personal private information over the internet for it not been totally safe. Mean score of 3.6 revealed that users feared that other people may be able to access their account when using cashless transactions. It was also found out that users are afraid of sending sensitive information online as it does not give them secured feeling with a Mean score of 3.4.

Conclusion

In this paper, perceived risks- Financial, Performance and Security risks negatively affects the behaviour of users towards adopting and continued usage of cashless transactions. Efforts should therefore be placed on them to assure users of safeguarding their money and private information.

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